

The impact of public financing on performance indicators of elementary education in Morocco

L'impact du financement public sur les indicateurs de performance de l'enseignement primaire au Maroc

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SUMMARY

The methodology to approach the field of education depends on the quality analysis and, above all, on its impact on the internal performance of the system and on the evaluation of different development policies. Meanwhile, it is important to take into account the macroeconomic and budgetary aspects that determine and resources available to reinforce the education system and the constraints as well. Hence, this analysis should focus on indicators that are assimilated into a methodological repertoire of several parameters that intentionally affect political decisions.

The main objective of this article relies on valuing the use of analyses and econometric techniques in the field of social sciences. In particular for the realization of an analytical study and a forecasting study, in an attempt to measure and evaluate the impact of public financing of elementary education in Morocco and its impact on performance indicators, from a longitudinal perspective of 40 years, covering the period from 1979 to 2018.

KEYWORDS: funding - indicators - education - regression - forecasting.

RÉSUMÉ

La méthodologie pour traiter la question de l'éducation dépend généralement de la qualité de l'analyse et surtout de sa portée sur le rendement interne de ce système et sur l'évaluation des différentes politiques en matière de développement. Par ailleurs, il est important de prendre en compte les aspects macroéconomiques et budgétaires qui déterminent les contraintes et les ressources disponibles pour renforcer le système éducatif. En outre, cette analyse devrait porter sur des indicateurs qui sont assimilés dans un répertoire méthodologique de plusieurs paramètres affectant intentionnellement des décisions politiques.

L'intérêt de cet article consiste à mettre en valeur l'utilisation des analyses et des techniques économétriques dans le domaine des sciences sociales, notamment la réalisation d'une étude analytique et une étude prévisionnelle, afin d'évaluer et de mesurer l'impact du financement public de l'enseignement primaire au Maroc et ses impacts sur les indicateurs de performance, dans une perspective longitudinale de 40 ans, couvrant la période 1979-2018.

MOTS CLÉS : financement - indicateurs - enseignement – régression – prévision.

Introduction

In Morocco, an impressive quantitative progress has been achieved since the country's independence through infrastructure extension and increasing access to basic social services. However, it should be noted that the most significant progress in terms of access to basic social services has been recently achieved, during the last decade, whereas the deficiencies affecting the development of the rural world are widely acknowledged by the political authorities (Tawil and & al, 2010).

As a result, the Moroccan state is making considerable efforts to reform the education system, since the topic of education is becoming increasingly important and as awareness grows that school is the best indicator for measuring a country's progress and advancement (Van Daele, 1993). Yet, from the beginning of the 1980s, the educational system entered a period of prolonged multidimensional crisis (Gerard, 2001).

It, therefore, seems necessary to gather fact collections, observations and analyses that permit to lead a comparison so as to deduce proven principles and major modifications, which will introduce new regulations in the educational system and also a set of effective rules so that education can develop in a positive direction (Novoa, 1995).

It seems clear that the quality of analysis and, above all, its scope are strongly linked to the working methodology, which deals mainly with the overall context in which the subject of education is situated. After considering the different development policies, it is crucial to take into account the macroeconomic and budgetary aspects that define the limitations and resources available to the educational system (Bernard & al, 2010).

Thus, analysis in education should lead to proposing a framework for assessing the impact of the efforts implemented by different education policies and determining the extent to which these policies affect the country's growth potential.

The comparison of needs and resources and their possible changes provides the overall framework for educational policy. The evolution of enrolments should be studied in order to measure how far we have come and how far we still have to go. Therefore, the analysis of repetition and dropout provides information on the internal efficiency of the different levels of education (Bernard & al, 2010).

Today, the effectiveness of the potential windfall from the demofigureic transition as a tangible dividend for economic and human development is, therefore, largely linked to the country's capacity to reform the educational and training system aiming at reducing persistent

quantitative deficits, improving internal efficiency and enabling beneficiaries to adapt to increasingly demanding labor market demands (HCP, 2015).

Moreover, the education system is categorized according to indicators that claim to measure their level of progress because they represent a dashboard that allows the construction of a reforming approach with conceptual and practical dimensions and whose coherence is always to be found in an ideology of progress.

In this sense, the analysis of indicators must be assimilated into a methodological repertoire of several parameters intentionally affecting policy decisions. The ways in which education, in the broadest sense, influences economic growth are multiple and fairly well identified, so we should not merely recall them, but rather highlight their major impact.

The organizational chart of the Ministry allows the distribution of administrative, pedagogical and financial tasks at central (central), regional (Regional Academies of Education and Training, AREFs), provincial (Provincial Directions) and local level (schools). Currently, there are 12 AREFs with one AREF per region of the Kingdom of Morocco. (Mezene & al. 2019).

This research focuses on the public financing of primary education in Morocco and its impacts in a 40-year longitudinal perspective, covering the period 1979-2018. This period is important because it witnessed major changes in public financing and in the configuration of the education system in general. The research consists mainly of the analysis of relevant data published by the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS). Thus, there is a question that is challenging:

What is the impact of public financing in terms of improving the performance indicators of primary education in Morocco?

In order to respond to this central query, this article will be deployed along three main lines. First, there will be a review of the theoretical approaches dealing with the main concepts of this theme. Secondly, the research methodology will be discussed and the way the research data has been analyzed. Finally, the results of the research study will be displayed and the main conclusions drawn so as to highlight any new horizons for future studies.

1. Theoretical overview

The fact that public sector products are in many ways intangible and immaterial makes it difficult to define a supply function in the conventional sense whereas the fact that public sector organizations produce goods that are free at the point of use means that product prices

are not determined by market forces. Since economic efficiency cannot be directly measured, a technique is needed to establish an efficiency frontier that would allow relatively accurate benchmarking (Sutherland and al, 2007).

The renewed goals of universal primary education have necessarily led to the problem of the costs and financing of education. The debate on the possible levers of control and the expected effects undoubtedly makes it possible to improve knowledge on education systems and to do so while taking into account the objectives of quality and social justice (BOURDON, 2006).

According to a study by Kamal and Bener (2009), in several developing countries, high failure rates were preceded by repetition, which has become a distinctive feature of many primary education systems (Kamal and Bener, 2009). Similarly, Ndaruhutse shows that, in both developed and developing countries, there are strong links between repetition and dropout, and that children who repeat classes are more likely to drop out of school in future years (Ndaruhutse, 2008).

In this context, the multilateral agencies make recommendations on the one hand on the control of education expenditure, through their increase, the reduction of unit costs, the improvement of teaching conditions and the reallocation of education expenditure towards primary education, and on the other hand, in favor of the mobilization of public, private and external resources (Henaff, 2003).

The World Bank defines education performance indicators as measures of the different components of a programme (inputs, processes, outputs) for regular and consistent monitoring. For Poister, these indicators are only quantitative in nature (raw figures - volume, average, ratio - ratios, scores, index, rates, percentages) and relate to the components of the programme (HURTEAU and RAICHE, 2005).

In several analytical articles, such as those on rates of return, the authors did not draw conclusions on the transfer of resources from education to other sectors of economy, or vice versa, but suggested a redistribution between different levels of education. Although most of them recognized that the objectives and benefits of education are not only economic, they suggested that the economic consequences of investments in education should be estimated before decisions are made (Schiefelbein, 1983).

The literature on the economics of education provides evidence to this effect on several dimensions of education policy: financing and access (Heckman et al.; Carneiro et al.; Lee;

Sauer; Buchinsky and Leslie), measures to counter school dropout (Dagenais et al.; Belzil et Hansen), the role of taxation (Heckman et al.), education vouchers (Ferreyra) and affirmative action (Arcidiacono) (Joanis, 2002).

According to Belzil and Hansen, to answer the question: how governments can reduce the incidence of school dropout among youth, it is important to target incentives by focusing on individuals who have absolute labor market advantages, high returns to experience, low preference for education and/or relatively low returns to education (Belzil & Hansen, 2002).

2. Method

To analyze the impact of public financing on the performance indicators of primary education in Morocco, an empirical approach was followed based on a quantitative approach. Data was extracted for the 40-year-old Moroccan education system, covering the period 1979- 2018, from the database of the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS)¹.

Five indicators have been selected and deployed as follows:

- *Fundingp*: Initial government funding of primary education as a percentage of GDP (%);
- *Enrolmentp*: Primary school enrolment, both sexes (%);
- *Completionp*: Primary completion rate, both sexes (%);
- *Repetitionp*: Repetition rate in primary education (all levels), for both sexes (%);
- *Dropoutp*: Cumulative dropout rate to last grade of primary education, both sexes (%).

This analysis is based on two types of studies: the first study is analytical and the second is a forecasting study.

2.1. Analytical study

This study consists of modelling the impact of initial public financing of primary education on primary education performance indicators, including enrolment, completion rate, repetition rate and drop-out rate. This modelling is based on a linear regression between the explanatory variable (*Fundingp*) and the dependent variables (*Enrolmentp*, *Completionp*, *Repetitionp* and *Dropoutp*).

This linear model is reached by adding an assumption of normality of residuals. The underlying idea is that there is a true unknown value θ . According to the Central Limit Theorem, this estimate tends on average towards the true value of θ . $\hat{\theta}$ is therefore a random variable whose distribution is going to be looked for. Thus, the hypothesis of normality of the

¹ The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) is the official and reliable source of internationally comparable data on education, science, culture and communication. <http://uis.unesco.org/fr>.

residuals comes back to posit that the n components e_1, \dots, e_n in of the vector e are independent observations of a random variable E distributed according to a distribution $N(0, \sigma^2)$, with σ^2 unknown (Chouquet, 2009).

The simple linear regression model is given by a y -vector of \mathbb{R}^n such as (Myers, 1986):

$$Y_i = \theta_0 + \theta_1 X_i + e$$

Where X is a matrix (n, k) of rank k ;

θ is an unknown vector of \mathbb{R}^k ;

e is a vector of n independent realizations of an absolute value normal of mean 0 and variance σ^2 unknown.

We use STATA 15.0 software under Windows and approach the data without any assumptions in advance; we examine what the data have to give.

2.2. Forecasting study

This study consists of modelling the time series of the four primary education performance indicators (*Enrolment, Completion, Repetition and Drop-out*) between 1979 and 2018. The analysis by an econometric model allows a good understanding of a series and to find the various explanatory factors.

This modelling is based on stochastic models. The most frequently used class of such models is the SARIMA model class (and its sub-models ARIMA, ARMA...). Thus, this modeling here focuses on the shape of the process (ε_t) . It leads to linear autoregressive models, of ARMA (p, q) type which is given by (Burtschy & Menendian, 1980) :

$$\varepsilon_t = a_1 X_{t-1} + \dots + a_p X_{p-1} + z_t + \theta_1 z_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q z_{q-1}$$

The treatments related to the identification, estimation, forecasting of our model are executed under the ITSM software, which is a time series analysis and forecasting software based on the Box and Jenkins method. It consists of eight programs (of unequal length); the three most important are “Pest”, “Trans” and “Arar” (Borgard and Guegan, 1996).

Our Modeling is based on the Autoregressive moving average ARMA (p, q) model which is first written in long moving average form; the parameters are then estimated by the innovation method, then the estimators of the ARMA (p, q) model are given by identification (Peter and al, 2002). The estimation method chosen is the least squares method, so the estimation is done in two steps: preliminary estimation, then fine estimation, even the software gives the

estimated values with their standard deviations.

Forecasts are made at the end of the observation of the series. First the forecast values of the centred ARMA process are available, then the non-centred process (possibly after inversion of the Box and Cox transformation). The software provides the calculation elements to build the prediction intervals.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Analytical study

3.1.1. Enrolment rate

Using STATA 15.0 software, we modelled using a linear regression model in which the enrolment rate (*Enrolmentp*) depends on the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*). The results are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Linear regression results for the variables Enrolmentp and Fundingp

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. regress enrolmentp fundingp
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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	40
Model	5146.85733	1	5146.85733	F(1, 38)	=	44.56
Residual	4388.93713	38	115.498345	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.5397
				Adj R-squared	=	0.5276
Total	9535.79446	39	244.50755	Root MSE	=	10.747

enrolmentp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
fundingp	41.02853	6.146144	6.68	0.000	28.58631 53.47074
_cons	-5.154381	12.04225	-0.43	0.671	-29.53264 19.22388

Source: Authors.

To assess the goodness of fit of the model to the data, we look at criterion R^2 , which represents the share of variance of y explained. According to the " R-squared " (0.5397), and " Adjusted R-squared " (0.5276), 53% of the variation in the enrolment rate (*Enrolmentp*) can be explained by variations in the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*). It can be seen that the variable (*Fundingp*) is significant (t-stat of 6.86 is higher than the threshold value of 1.96), and the P-value is less than 5% ($0.000 < 0.05$).

Thus the Fisher statistic calculated is $F = 44.56$ and the associated probability is less than 5% ($0.0000 < 0.05$), so the explanatory variable has an influence on the dependent variable and

the model is globally significant.

Figure 1: The regression line for the variables Enrolmentp and Fundingp

Source: Authors

The equation for this linear regression model is:

$$y_i = -5.15 + 41.03x_i$$

According to figure 1 of the scatter plot with the regression line of two variables and the regression line of two variables, we observe that the correlation between the two variables is positive, which means that the values of primary school enrolment rates tend to increase when those of public financing increase.

3.1.2. Completion rate

The results of the linear regression model in which the completion rate (*Completiontp*) with the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*) are represented in the following table 2:

Table 2: Linear regression results for the variables Completiontp and Fundingp

. regress completionp fundingp

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	40
Model	6162.4908	1	6162.4908	F(1, 38)	=	27.01
Residual	8671.19614	38	228.189372	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.4154
				Adj R-squared	=	0.4001
Total	14833.6869	39	380.350947	Root MSE	=	15.106

completionp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
fundingp	44.89448	8.638982	5.20	0.000	27.40578 62.38319
_cons	-21.99042	16.92651	-1.30	0.202	-56.25635 12.27551

Source: Authors

According to the " R-squared " (0.4154), and " Adjusted R-squared " (0.4001), i.e. 40% of the variation in the (*Completiontp*) enrolment rate can be explained by variations in the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*). It can be seen that the variable (*Fundingp*) is significant (t-stat of 5.20 is higher than the threshold value of 1.96), and the P-value is less than 5% (0.000 < 0.05).

Thus the Fisher statistic calculated is F= 27.01 and the associated probability is less than 5% (0.0000 < 0.05), so the explanatory variable has an influence on the dependent variable and the model is globally significant.

Figure 2: The regression line for the variables Completiontp and Fundingp

Source: Authors

The equation for this linear regression model is :

$$y_i = -21.99 + 44.89 x_i$$

According to figure 2 of the scatter plot with the regression line of two variables, we observe that the correlation between the two variables is positive, which means that the values of primary completion rates tend to increase when those of public financing increase.

3.1.3. Repetition rate

The results of the linear regression model in which the repetition rate (*Repetitionp*) with the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*) are shown in the following table 3:

Table 3: Linear regression results for the variables Repetitionp and Fundingp

. regress repetitionp fundingp

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	40
Model	38.1276299	1	38.1276299	F(1, 38)	=	0.84
Residual	1723.72643	38	45.3612218	Prob > F	=	0.3650
Total	1761.85406	39	45.1757451	R-squared	=	0.0216
				Adj R-squared	=	-0.0041
				Root MSE	=	6.7351

repetitionp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
fundingp	-3.531301	3.851742	-0.92	0.365	-11.32875 4.266143
_cons	21.77754	7.546787	2.89	0.006	6.499872 37.05522

Source: Authors

The "R-squared" (0.0216) is very low to justify the relationship between the repetition rate (*Repetitionp*) and the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*). Similarly, the variable (*Fundingp*) is not significant (the absolute t-stat value of 0.92 is lower than the threshold value of 1.96), and the P-value is higher than 5% (0.365>0.05).

Thus the Fisher statistic calculated is F= 0.84 and the associated probability is greater than 5% (0.3650> 0.05), so the explanatory variable has no influence on the dependent variable and the model is globally insignificant.

Figure 3: The regression line for the variables *Repetitionp* and *Fundingp*

Source: Authors

The equation for this linear regression model is as follows:

$$y_i = 21.78 - 3.53x_i$$

According to figure 3 of the scatterplot with the regression line of two variables, we observe that the correlation between the two variables is negative. Similarly, as the model is not significant, the relationship between the repetition rate in primary education and public financing of this level of education cannot be justified.

3.1.4. Dropout rate

The results of the linear regression model in which the cumulative drop-out rate in primary education (*Droppoutp*) with the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*) are shown in the following table:

Table 4: Linear regression results for the variables Dropout and Fundingp

. regress dropoutp fundingp

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	40
Model	890.738158	1	890.738158	F(1, 38)	=	15.33
Residual	2208.19473	38	58.1103876	Prob > F	=	0.0004
Total	3098.93289	39	79.4598176	R-squared	=	0.2874
				Adj R-squared	=	0.2687
				Root MSE	=	7.623

dropoutp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
fundingp	-17.06828	4.359551	-3.92	0.000	-25.89373 -8.242836
_cons	55.3307	8.541745	6.48	0.000	38.03884 72.62256

Source: Authors

According to the "R-squared" (0.2874), and "Adjusted R-squared" (0.2687), i.e. 27% of the variation in (*Dropoutp*), the enrolment rate can be explained by variations in the initial public financing of primary education (*Fundingp*). It can be seen that the variable (*Fundingp*) is significant (the absolute value of t-stat of 3.92 is higher than the threshold value of 1.96), and the P-value is less than 5% ($0.000 < 0.05$).

Thus the Fisher statistic calculated is $F = 15.33$ and the associated probability is less than 5% ($0.0004 < 0.05$), so the explanatory variable has an influence on the dependent variable and the model is globally significant.

Figure 4: The regression line for variables Dropout and Fundingp

Source: Authors

The equation for this linear regression model is :

$$y_i = 55.33 - 17.07x_i$$

According to figure 4 of the scatter plot with the regression line of two variables, it is clear that the correlation between the two variables is negative, which means that the values of the dropout rates in primary education tend to decrease when those of public financing increase. This modelling allows us to conclude that the increase in the initial public financing of primary education will have a positive impact on the increase in the enrolment rate and the primary completion rate. Moreover, this increase has a considerable effect on reducing the dropout rate. On the other hand, the increase in initial public financing of primary education will have no impact on the pupil repetition rate, which may be explained by other variables linked to other indicators of the internal quality of the Moroccan education system.

3.2. Forecasting study

3.2.1. Enrolment rate

Using ITSM software, the time series (Figure 5) representing the 40-year values of the enrolment rate can be modelled; the data (see left side in Figure 5) are clearly not stationary. Both level and volatility increase over time, and there appears to be a significant seasonal component. They must therefore be transformed in order to be represented as a realization of a stationary time series using one or more of the transformations available for this purpose in

ITSM.

Consequently, after transformation, differentiation and also parameter estimation, the best model, the one that minimizes the AICC selection criterion (Peter and al, 2006) is accepted.

Finally, here is the ARMA (1,0) model:

$$X(t) = 0.6347 X(t-1) + Z(t)$$

The following figure shows the initial fluctuation of our series with the 12 future values (until 2030) between a range of maximum possible values and minimum possible values.

Figure 5 : Evolution of the enrolment rate and its forecast

Source: Authors

Table 5 shows the numerical values of 12 predicted values and also the minimum possible values (Lower) and the maximum possible values (Upper).

Table 5: Forecast values of the variable enrolment rate

Step	Prediction	Lower	Upper
1	101	95	108
2	102	90	116
3	102	85	123
4	106	83	135
5	107	80	143
6	107	76	150
7	108	74	158
8	108	71	165
9	110	70	172
10	111	68	180
11	114	68	191
12	117	67	202

Source: Authors

According to the values of the primary school enrolment rate forecast, it is noticed that there is an upward progression of this rate from one year to another, and the forecasts also mention that this rate will have exceeded the value of 100% from the first year of this forecast.

Thus, Morocco will be able to achieve an objective of the strategic vision which stipulates that, by 2030, the country will be able to ensure that all girls and boys complete a full cycle of free, quality primary education on an equal footing, equipping them with genuinely useful skills (CSEFRS, 2004).

3.2.2. Completion rate

The time series (figure 6) representing the 40-year values of the primary completion rate is modelled in the same predictive manner. The modelling of this series gives the following ARMA (1,0) model:

$$X(t) = 0.05613X(t-1) + Z(t)$$

Figure 6: Evolution of the completion rate and its forecast

Source: Authors

The extraction of numerical values from 12 forecast values is presented in the following table 6:

Table 6: Forecast values of the variable completion rate

Step	Prediction	Lower	Upper
1	96	86	107
2	98	83	114
3	100	82	121
4	102	81	128
5	104	104	134
6	107	81	141
7	109	81	147
8	111	81	154
9	114	81	160
10	116	81	167
11	119	81	174
12	122	82	180

Source: Authors

As for the primary school enrolment rate, according to the forecast values of the primary completion rate, there is an upward progression of this rate from one year to another, and the forecasts also indicate that this rate will have reached the value of 100% in the third year of this forecast.

3.2.3. Repetition rate

The time series (figure 7) representing the 40-year values of the primary school repetition rate is modelled in the same predictive manner. The modelling of this series gives the following ARMA (2,1) model:

$$X(t) = -0.9218 X(t-1) - 0.1851 X(t-2) + Z(t) + 1.095 Z(t-1)$$

Figure 7: Trends in the repetition rate and its forecast

Source: Authors

The extraction of the numerical values of 12 forecast values is presented in the following table 7:

Table 7: Predicted values of the variable repetition rate

Step	Prediction	Lower	Upper
1	10.9	8.6	13.9
2	10.7	7.4	15.4
3	10.8	7.1	16.4
4	8.4	5.1	13.7
5	7.6	4.4	13.0
6	9.8	5.4	17.7
7	10.5	5.5	19.7
8	10.5	5.3	20.7
9	11.4	5.5	23.3
10	12.7	6.0	27.1
11	12.7	5.8	28.0
12	13.3	5.8	30.3

Source: Authors

According to the forecast values of the cumulative repetition rate in primary education, there is a downward progression of this rate up to the fifth year of this forecast with a value of 7.6%. After this year, this rate will continue to increase up to 12.7% at the end of the year 2030.

In order to avoid this upward trend in the repetition rate, the Ministry's efforts must focus on strengthening the production and implementation within schools of teaching mechanisms, personalized monitoring of pupils, provision of teaching support for pupils who need it, and sessions to bring learning up to standard. On the other hand, support for this mechanism mainly through mobilization, awareness raising and training of actors: (school heads, teachers, parents, local authorities and associations).

3.2.4. Dropout rate

The time series (figure 8) representing the 40-year values of the primary school dropout rate is modelled in the same predictive manner. The modelling of this series gives the following

ARMA (2,0) model:

$$X(t) = -0.1882 X(t-1) - 0.3780 X(t-2) + Z(t)$$

Figure 8: Evolution of the dropout rate and its forecast

Source: Authors

The extraction of the numerical values of 12 forecast values is presented in the following table 8:

Table 8: Predicted values of the dropout rate

Step	Prediction	Lower	Upper
1	5.2	3.2	8.7
2	4.4	2.3	8.5
3	1.9	1.0	3.9
4	2.0	0.9	4.3
5	2.0	0.9	4.7
6	1.4	0.6	3.4
7	1.7	0.6	4.3
8	1.6	0.6	4.3
9	1.0	1.0	2.8
10	0.6	0.6	1.9
11	0.8	0.8	2.6
12	0.7	0.7	2.3

Source: Authors

According to the forecast values of the primary school dropout rate, there is a downward progression of this rate until the last year of this forecast with a value of 0.7%. However, major efforts still need to be maintained to eliminate this phenomenon, including the removal of socio-economic and geographical barriers that hinder access to compulsory education, and the promotion of learner retention by combating the main causes of dropping out.

Conclusion

This research attempts to consolidate the fact that the state should give special importance to the education sector, either by increasing the share of funding for the sector or by mobilizing other resources, especially for the primary cycle. These measures will have a great impact on the improvement of performance indicators for this cycle.

Accordingly, Morocco has in recent years put in place a coherent set of targeted, priority and fundamental actions that aim essentially at making up for the delays noted in the implementation of the National Charter for Education and Training. Notably with a view to extend the territorial coverage and intake capacity of primary and lower secondary schools in order to provide a seat for every student and to bring schools closer to the population.

This conclusion will be approved by a provisional note, which will stipulate the generalization of primary education at 100% in the near future. In addition, even the completion rate, which is positively increasing, could reach 100% in 2022, but this rate hides a very important reality concerning the repetition rate, which remains very alarming.

Likewise, for the primary school dropout rate, this forecast will stipulate a downward progression of this rate to 0.7% in 2030. But in order to accomplish this achievement and eradicate this phenomenon, it is necessary to continue to strengthen measures that seek significantly to reduce the impact of socio-economic or geographical factors that hinder access to education and are some of the main causes of non-enrolment and drop-out. These measures consist of developing the provision of boarding schools, canteens and school transport as well as various material aids.

This research, in its ultimate goal, aims to help decision makers to have a global vision on the functioning of the education system, and to guide sectoral development efforts, decentralized and controlled, in order to obtain the necessary synergies for the expansion of the entire school system.

References

1. Belzil, C. & Hansen, J. (2002). Unobserved Ability and the Return to Schooling. *Econometrica*, 70(5), 2075-2091. Retrieved January 4, 2020, from www.jstor.org/stable/3082032.
2. Bernard, J.M. Beïfith Kouak, T.N. kengne, A.P. & Klaus, J. (2010). Guide méthodologique d'analyse de la question enseignante. Ed. *Regional Office for Education in Africa*, UNESCO.
3. Borgard, F. and Guegan, D. (1996). Études de séries chronologiques linéaires à temps discret. Comparaison de logiciels. *Revue de statistique appliquée*, tome 44, n° 4, p. 59-80
4. Bourdon, J. (2006). Coût et financement de l'éducation primaire en Afrique Subsaharienne. *Les Collections du CEPED, Série Rencontres*, Paris.
5. Burtschy, B. and Menendian, C. (1980). About short-term forecasting of industrial production. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, Vol. 28, No. 2, pp.5-24.
6. Chouquet, C. (2009). Modèles linéaires. Éd. *Laboratoire de Statistique et Probabilités - Université Paul Sabatier - Toulouse*, France.
7. CSEFRS (2014). Vision stratégique de la réforme éducative 2015-2030. Le Conseil Supérieur de l'Éducation, de la Formation et de la Recherche Scientifique (CSEFRS), Morocco.
8. Gerard, E. (2001). La demande d'éducation en Afrique : approches sociologiques. *Réseaux thématiques de recherche de l'UEPA*, N°1.
9. HCP, (2015). Le Maroc entre Objectifs du Millénaire pour le Développement et Objectifs de Développement Durable. Rapport National *Haut-Commissariat Au Plan*, Morocco, p.17.
10. Henaff, N. (2003). Quel financement pour l'École en Afrique?. *Cahiers d'études africaines*, XLIII (1-2), 169-170.
11. Hurteau, M. and Raiche, G. (2005). Des indicateurs de performance utiles et pertinents. Éd. *Association québécoise de pédagogie collégiale*, N°25, Colloque AQPC – Le Cégep.
12. Joanis, M. (2002). The economics of education: methodologies, findings and lessons. Ed. *CIRANO*, Act of Conference on the Econometrics of Education: Modeling Selectivity and Outcomes, *Les cahiers de la série scientifique*, no 2002s-70, Montreal.
13. Kamal, M. et Bener, A. (2009). Factors contributing to school failure among school children in very fast developing Arabian Society. *Oman Medical Journal*, Volume 24.
14. Mezene, M. El Kamli, M. and El Ouadighi, S. (2019) « Analytical study on the contribution of the adoption of the project management mode in the evolution of the level of governance of the Moroccan education system » *Revue Internationale des Sciences de Gestion* « Numéro 3 : Avril 2019 / Volume 2 : numéro 2 » p : 820 – 836.
15. Myers, R. H. (1986). Classical and modern regression with applications. Ed. *Duxbury Press*.
16. Nadoveza Jelić, O. & Gardijan Kedžo, M. (2018). Efficiency vs effectiveness: an analysis of tertiary education across Europe. *Public Sector Economics*, 42(4), 381 – 414.

17. Ndaruhutse, S. (2008). Grade repetition in primary schools in Sub-Saharan Africa: An evidence base for change. *Center for British Teachers (CfBT) Education Trust*, pp1-76.
18. Novoa, A. (1995). Models of analysis in comparative education: the field and the map. *University of Lisbon*.
19. Peter J. B., Richard A. and Davis, R. J. (2002). Introduction to Time Series and Forecasting, Volume 1. *Ed. Springer, USA*.
20. Peter J. B., Richard A. and Davis, R. J. (2006). Time Series: Theory and Methods. . Ed. Springer, USA. *Revue de statistique appliquée*, Vol. 44, No. 4, pp. 59-80.
21. Schiefelbein, E. (1983). Educational Financing in Developing Countries: Research Findings and Contemporary Issues. *Ed. International Development Research Centre, Ottawa, Canada*.
22. Sutherland, D., Price, R. Joumard, I. and Nicq N. (2007). Performance indicators for public spending efficiency in primary and secondary education Economics. *Department Working Paper*, No. 546, OECD.
23. Tawil, S., Cerbelle, S. et Alama, A. (2010) Education au Maroc : Analyse du secteur. UNESCO, Bureau multipays pour le Maghreb, p.17.
24. The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) is the official and reliable source of internationally comparable data on education, science, culture and communication. <http://uis.unesco.org/fr>.
25. Van Daele, H. (1993). Comparative éducation. *Ed. Presses Universitaire de France (Quesais-je?)*, Paris.